

Galician Forest Administration

Wood products value chain tracing

FORTRA is a QR-code product label allowing consumers to access information on a wooden product including carbon footprint and the forests of origin

Highlights of innovative features

- Valorization of sustainable wooden products through increase of transparency and decision support for customers.
- The transparency is guaranteed through blockchain technology.
- The FORTRA tool is available in English, Spanish and Galician and could easily be extended to other languages and countries.
- The tool may be further expanded into the entire life-cycle of the product (repair, reuse, refurbish, recycle) fostering a circular bioeconomy in the region.

The final product displays a QR-code through which the customer accesses product information including manufacturing company, location of the forest of origin, cutting license and application date, wood volume used for the product, certification stamp, carbon footprint, regeneration after felling and all process operations of the transformation into the final product.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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